

SOME CONSIDERATIONS REGARDING THE EXPRESSION AND COMPOSITION OF EXCLAMATIONS.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8040397>

Annotation: *in this article, some opinions and opinions are expressed on the topic of the sentence, its specifics, simple sentences and complicated simple sentences, the views of some linguists on these issues, the characteristic of exclamations, exclamations, the expression and composition of exclamations.*

Keywords: *sentence, simple sentences, complicated simple sentences, unit, exclamation, articulation of exclamations, composition of exclamations, simple, spread, complex, native exclamations.*

INTRODUCTION

It is known that human speech is the greatest of all the blessings given to it, people bring into existence through their speech all that is formed in the mind of thoughts, goals, in general. And the sentence, expressing a certain opinion, forms part of human speech. Sentences can vary in terms of their structural structure, i.e. simple, compound, complex representations. According to the structure of sentences, these types have their own characteristics, which differ from each other in terms of the features of formation, formative means, scope of meaning of thought. One of the most used types of sentences in our speech is simple ones. Simple sentences are the smallest but important syntactic unit that performs a communicative function. In the formation of other types of sentences according to their construction, that is, complex simple sentences, compound sentences, complex compound sentences, simple sentences also occupy an important place as a basis. There are certain grammatical signs of being a sentence. In any sentence, regardless of whether it consists of one word or many words, the relative thought completion and the existence of predicativity, formed grammatically by certain laws and rules, must have a specific intonation (tone). Syntactic units consisting of a single word or several words corresponding to the above requirements are sentences. The sentence will be composed of words and phrases tshkil. However, in speech, simple sentences will also contain parts that do not enter into syntactic contact with sentence fragments. While they do not perform a task as a separate piece, but add thought to one degree or another to the thought they perceive from the sentence. As a result, a complication event occurs in the sentence structure. In the textbook, manual and scientific literature, this type of sentence is called “complicated simple sentences.”

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METDOLOGY.

The fact that complicated simple sentences themselves are a separate syntactic phenomenon is demonstrated in Russian linguistics by A.R. Based by Rudnev. In Uzbek linguistics, however, the complicated question of simple propositions is G'. Abdurahmanov, H. Mahmudov, H. Boltaboyeva, B. Yuzbayev, G'. The theory was also worked out in practical terms by the abdurahmanovs, some opinions and comments were expressed on them. In addition, there are tools that make complicated simple sentences more complicated, formative, of course. In the book “Grammar of the Uzbek language”, the term “complex sentence” was applied to these syntactic units, the structural formation of which is described as follows: “in complex syntax, syntactic constructions and categories

are studied that come in the composition of a simple sentence and turn them into a complex sentence. These are: separated sentence segments, exclamations, introductory segments”

The structural structure of these syntactic units in the textbook "Current Uzbek Literary Language" by A. Gulomov, M. Askarova is shown as follows: "Elements complicating a simple sentence are different: cohesive clauses, separate clauses, introductory constructions and introductory constructions and incentives"

In G. Abdurahmnov's textbook "Grammar of the Uzbek language" we can see the view of the above book "Grammar of the Uzbek language" (detached clause, imperative, introductory clauses).

B. Orinboyev's textbook "Current Uzbek Literary Language" includes the following as means of complicating simple sentences: compound clauses, impulses, input and input devices, separated clauses, adjectival, adverbial clauses, action systems.

In this, complicating agents are given in detail. As shown in the textbook "Current Uzbek Literary Language" by A. Gulomov, M. Askarova, the unitary clauses are included as a means of forming complex simple sentences.

N. Mahmudov and A. Nurmonov consider impulses, input and input devices, separate clauses, adjective and adverb clauses, systems named action, and participial **sentences as complex sentences.**

RESULTS

From the above, we can understand that in the syntax of a complicated simple sentence, the syntactic devices and categories that come into the structure of the sentence and turn them into a complex sentence are studied. They are as follows: separate parts of the sentence, impulses, introductions and introductions. In this article, we want to talk about one of the constructions that create complicated simple sentences, impulses, their characteristics, expression and composition. Impulse - shows the relationship between the speaker and the listener. The relationship of the speaker to the listener is established by addressing and urging. The word expressing this kind of attitude and encouragement of the speaker or listener is called "incentive" in grammar. In a broad sense, the adverb indicates the process of speech aimed at whom or what, and in a narrow sense it means the person or object to which the speech of the speaker is directed.

Through the imperative, the speaker's speech is focused on individuals. In order to achieve a certain goal, the speaker urges and appeals to the listener. Accordingly, the word that is the expression of the person who is addressed and encouraged becomes an exhortation.

DISCUSSION

Adverbs mainly come in the form of the head agreement. In this respect, he looks like an owner. But adverbs differ from possessors by consonant intonation, pauses, and lack of syntactic connection with participles. Adverbs express the person to whom the speaker's speech is directed: forgive me, mother, I was buried in work (Ya). Adverbs can be expressed in the Uzbek language by different groups of words. They are represented by category words as follows:

- 1) ot bilan: Bilasizmi, Ikrom, ko‘klam shabodasi yurib qoldi (S.A.).
- 2) otlashgan sifat bilan: Xo‘sh, yaxshilar, nima qilmoq darkor? (O.Yo.).
- 3) otlashgan son bilan: Uchinchilar, yakuniy nazoratlarga yaxshi tayyorgarlik ko‘ring!
- 4) otlashgan sifatdoshlar bilan: Ey, sportda g‘olib chiqqanlar, sizlarga shon-sharoflar bo‘lsin!
- 5) undov bilan: Hoy, seni kutib turishibdi.
- 6) frazeologizm bilan: Xayr, o‘g‘lim, oq yo‘l bo‘lsin, xayr, ko‘zim qorasi (H.O.).

7) bir butun holda qo'llanadigan bog'lamlar bilan: Butun dunyo tinchliksevarlari, birlashingiz!

Impulses differ in terms of structural structure. Based on the research carried out in Uzbek linguistics, we can divide them into the following groups.

1. Single urges
2. Common urges
3. Complex motivations
4. Organized urges.

1. The speech of the speaker is focused on a person or an object. The words denoting the name of the person or object to which the thought is directed act as adverbs. from nouns, either singular or plural:

To'kilgandan tomchilagan yomon, uka, tomchilagan.(A.Q.)

Amin bo'l, qizaloq, unutmaymiz hech,

Zafar kunlarida yodlanar noming. (Uyg'un).

Mamlakat emas Mirzacho'l. (G'.G'.)

Og'a, ayamga xat yozibsiz-ku? (A.Q.)

Dada-chi, dada, bugun biz poyezd-poyezd o'ynadik.(A.Q.)

2. Common urges

The speaker's speech is focused on a person or an object. The words that indicate the person or object to whom the speech is addressed are used as exhortations. These impulses can come with their own determiners and interpreters. Such impulses are common impulses. If one of the elements in the common impulses is considered an impulse, the rest are the determiners and interpreters of this impulse. Some of the common impulses are syntactic units, some are phraseological units. will find content. Some of the elements in the syntactic combination of the common impulse have freedom in their semantic and grammatical relations, while others do not:

1.To'g'ri, o'rtoq Rahimjon , mix ham egilsa, to'g'irlab yana qoqiladi (A.Q.).

2.Yo'ling oydin, olganing oltin bo'lsin, aziz o'g'lim (G'.G'.).

3.Qishloq xo'jaligi xodimlari! Chorva mollari mahsuldorligini keskin suratda oshirishga va ularning sonini ko'paytirishga erishingiz.(O'.H).

3. Complex exclamations

The impulse can be complex as well as solitary and widespread. The speaker addresses his interlocutor, names him in different ways and expresses his attitude towards him. As a result, the object to which the speaker's speech is directed is one, and it is named differently. Thus, the adverb consists of words expressing different characteristics of the same object. These adverbs are complex adverbs and consist of two or more single adverbs:

Mehnat,muhabbatning, sharaf, nomusning xalqimiz qalbida

Tantanasi-chun, sipqoring,Azizlar,Do'stlar,Yoronlar... (G'G').

4. Efforts are also combined. Single urges consist of two or more urges and indicate that the speaker is urging several persons and objects at the same time. These urges differ from complex urges according to the amount of the object of urge, that is, in dull urges, the object of urge is many and complex. and in urges, the object of urge is one.

Hasan, Aziz, Ibrahim, unload the luggage immediately.

Surauya, Muhayya, Rana, Muqaddas, you make my eyes sparkle with satin!

CONCLUSION

Thus, our language is extremely beautiful and colorful. The sentences that create the communication process also differ from each other in terms of the structure and the scope of expression. In the emergence of such phenomena, along with other units, impulses are also involved. An impulse can be directed to one or several objects at the same time. If

an impulse consists of one word representing one object, it is a single impulse. Single prompts can come extended with qualifiers. In this case, the impulses are combined. If the adverb represents several objects or consists of several words representing one object, they are complex adverbs.

List of used literature.

1. Abdurahmanov G'. Grammar of the Uzbek language. T.: Science, 1996.
2. Mahmudov N., Nurmonova. Theoretical grammar of the Uzbek language. T.: 1995.
3. Ghulomova., Askarova M. Current Uzbek literary language. T.: Teacher, 1997.
4. Grammar of the Uzbek language. Episode 2.: Science, 1996.
5. Rudnev A. R. Syntax oslojnennogo predlojeniya. M, 1959.
6. Tursunov U., Mukhtorov J. Modern Uzbek. Morphology, Samarkand, 1960.
7. Suleymanov A. X. atov sentences, exclamations and vocative sentences in Uzbek, Samarkand, 1956.